

Momentum Versus Kinetic Energy/Energy in Kinematics Part 2

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In Part 1, we noted that if a particle at rest is given a push or pull (acted on by vector force), a velocity vector is created, but one may also postulate the existence of another vector p related to impact, because this same particle may later collide, with say a mirror or another particle, and create an impulse. We argued that this idea applies to a single impact at x, t in space which should take dt and so $dp/dt = F$. If, however, there are forces at each x, y, z , then there is a continuous change in the particle and one may write $v \cdot dp = F \cdot dr$. For $F = -\text{grad } V(x, y, z)$ one has path independence and should obtain a scalar function (in terms of rotation) related to the particle. Thus, there is a p vector and a rotational scalar linked to the particle and we used special relativity to find expressions for both.

Here we seek Probability(v_x, v_y, v_z), where v_x is the x component of velocity. In (1), this expression is written as Probability($[v]$) = $P(v_x)P(v_y)P(v_z)$ ((1)) where P =Probability and $[v]$ is the modulus. We suggest that one should indeed consider rotational invariance, i.e. $P([v])$, but it is not necessarily the case that $P([v])$ factors into $P(v_x)P(v_y)P(v_z)$. We note that a given transformation has an invariant quantity which is conserved. In the case of velocity, $v_x^2 + v_y^2 + v_z^2$ ((2)) is in fact an invariant of rotation (as is any function of it) and the form ((2)) is factorizable if $P([v]) = \exp(-a v \cdot v)$.

We note, however, that there may be other transformations at work which include rotational invariance and in fact have a different conserved quantity. We suggest that it is this more general transformation's invariant which must be considered and in general it will not be ((1)) and in general the factorizable form will not hold. Furthermore, it is not ultimately the invariant of a general transformation that one uses, but rather an invariant of the interaction. This invariant of the interaction, however, should be linked to the various symmetries (transformations and their invariants) in the problem.

We showed in Part 1, that if one considers the transformation based on viewing a particle at rest from a frame moving at constant $-v$, then r vector, t transforms to r' vector, t' , i.e. a vector and number transform. We suggested that rest mass is also a number in the rest frame and so should transform into E' , p' vector. The invariant in this case is not the simple form ((2)), but should respect rotational invariance. We expect that it is the more general invariant which should be involved in finding $P(v_x, v_y, v_z)$ and that this invariant should have physical meaning (i.e. it is the single particle energy). Finding this more general invariant, however, is not enough.

Collisions create $P(v_x, v_y, v_z)$ (i.e. equilibrium) and it is an invariant associated directly with the collision which must be used. We argue that p vector is conserved (through Lorentz transformation arguments) and then suggest that the associated E (because it Lorentz transforms as part of the p 4-vector) is also a candidate for conservation (in elastic collisions). E is chosen to govern $P(v_x, v_y, v_z)$, but at the same time one must consider the relation between E and v_x, v_y, v_z given by the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m^2 c^4$. Thus, interaction physics governs the actual conserved quantity one uses, but this is linked to invariants of transformational symmetry in the problem.

Probability $P(v_x, v_y, v_z)$

In Part 1, we sought a vector p and an accompanying number which is rotational invariant in velocity. We do not repeat the associated argument here except to note that it was not sufficient to consider rotational transformation, we had to consider the more general Lorentz transformation which respects rotational invariance.

In (1),

Probability (v_x, v_y, v_z) is written as: $P(v_x)P(v_y)P(v_z) = P([v])$ where $[v]$ is the modulus of v and $P = \text{Probability}$ ((2))

Rotational invariance must hold and v_x, v_y, v_z values are based on the choice of the co-ordinate system. We thus suggest that any v_x, v_y, v_z with the same modulus should have the same probability and write:

$$P(v_x, v_y, v_z) = P([v]) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) does not immediately mean that one may factor $P([v]) = P(v_x)P(v_y)P(v_z)$ mathematically. There is a solution:

$\exp(-a \cdot v \cdot v)$ which is factorizable, but other forms are not. ((5))

We note that $v \cdot v$ is the invariant associated with a rotational transformation, but this might not be the only transformation in question. For example, there might be a more general transformation which holds. This transformation should respect rotational invariance, but should most likely have a different invariant, and it is this invariant which should be considered as a conserved quantity. It should then be identifiable with a physical quantity, but this quantity is in fact constructed mathematically, just as Newton's kinetic energy is mathematically created from dp/dt with $p=mv$.

Identifying the most general transformation which applies and its corresponding invariant quantity seems to be key.

The Lorentz Transformation

Even though rotational invariance is important, we showed in Part 1 that there seems to be a second transformation at work. We consider r vector and t (x, t in one dimension) and argued that

$$X, t \rightarrow x', t' \quad ((6))$$

when a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t is viewed by a moving frame ($-v$). We noted that if $x=0, t=0$ and $x'=0, t'=0$ are the initial points, the $v = x'/t'$ and so x, t must transform. We then argued that one

had a situation in which a number t and vector r transformed and that m_0 is a number and so could transform in the same manner to produce:

$$P' \text{ vector and } E' \text{ number} \quad ((7))$$

This should be a more general transformation than a rotational one and find that an invariant is:

$$-EE + cc \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0 m_0 c^4 c^2 \quad ((8))$$

Given $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, we see that rotational invariance is respected and so one does in fact have a transformation which respects the first symmetry considered. The catch is that one should focus on the invariant of the more general transformation. One may show that:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v} / c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{p} = m_0 \mathbf{v} / \sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v} / c^2} \quad ((9))$$

One sees that the invariant does simply factor into $P(v_x)P(v_y)P(v_z)$. The question becomes: What is conserved in an interaction? We defined \mathbf{p} in the first place in Part 1 as describing the effect of a force on a particle such that this particle may later impart the force back to another particle or target in an impulse hit. \mathbf{p} vector is most certainly physical and it should be associated with a scalar under rotations. This scalar then should be E it seems. In other words, the invariant of the transformation is not enough, one must find a physically conserved quantity.

One may argue as Newton did that action-reaction implies that \mathbf{p} is conserved and so the accompanying E may also be considered as a potentially conserved quantity. E (energy) is always conserved, but is not always represented by only kinematics, i.e. there may be sound etc, but in an elastic collision kinematically E is conserved. If one considers elastic collisions in a gas, then one has a conserved E and this represented by:

$$\sqrt{\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} c^2 + m_0 m_0 c^4} \quad ((10))$$

In such a case, one does not have $P(v_x)P(v_y)P(v_z)$, but

$$\exp(-1/T E) \quad ((11))$$

It is only in the $v/c \ll 1$ limit that $E = m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v}$ and one may drop the constant $m_0 c^2$ and consider only $.5 m_0 \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v}$ which is the invariant of the rotational transformation.

Third Invariant

In the above sections we considered two transformations, a rotational and Lorentz one, each with their own invariant. Ultimately, however, it was a third invariant, namely E (energy) which was used to compute $P(v_x, v_y, v_z) = P(|\mathbf{v}|)$. In other words, the two transformations by themselves are not enough to solve the problem. We note that the Lorentz transformation is not simply connected with considering the motion of relative frames, it is also linked with

$$dp/dt = F \quad ((12))$$

It is ((12)) which is associated with an invariance if F and $-F$ (i.e. action reaction) occur in a reaction. The simplest situation is $F, -F$ acting on two particles of the same size. Initial and final momentum is the same both nonrelativistically and relativistically. Next, consider a single particle, moving with v , hit a second particle at rest in an elastic collision and bounce back causing the second particle to move to the right. If one assumes that momentum is conserved then the sum of momenta transforms as a Lorentz invariant. One may, however, add momentum in a given frame and treat this as the total momentum and apply a Lorentz transformation and so momentum should be conserved. If this is the case, then the associated energy E should have the possibility of being conserved as long as it does not contradict momentum conservation. For example, particles which merge convert kinematical energy into other energy forms.

As a result, one must consider an invariant which is linked with interactions as these govern equilibrium, but at the same time general transformations, such as the Lorentz one and rotational, exist and must also be taken into consideration.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that when dealing with probabilities $P(v_x, v_y, v_z)$, one must consider interactions which occur which establish the probability form, i.e. equilibrium. That being said, there are various transformations which may be linked to the problem. One is usually rotational invariance, but there is also the more general Lorentz transformation, which respects rotational symmetry. Interestingly, the Lorentz transformation is directly associated with an interaction because if one views a rest particle from a moving frame, it is seen as moving, but $dp/dt = F$ is used to set a particle into motion. The invariant of the Lorentz transformation must be considered, i.e. $E^2 - c^2 p \cdot p = \text{invariant}$, but at the same time one must find what is conserved in the actual collision. We argue that p vector is conserved and given that p and E transform the same way under a Lorentz transformation, E is a candidate for conservation in an interaction (as long as the interaction is elastic). Thus, physics governs the actual conserved quantity one uses, but this is linked to invariants of transformational symmetry in the problem.

References

1. Da Silva, M. et al Historical and epistemological perspective of the Kaniadakis distribution (2025) http://www.lajpe.org/mar25/19_1_03.pdf